

Figure S1: Alpha diversity in baseline vs. long-term samples

Shannon index compared between the baseline sample (defined as the earliest sample for each patient) and long-term samples (averaged when 2 long-term samples available). Patient IDs correspond to Figures 1 and 2. p value is from a paired Wilcoxon test.